

MECHANISMS FOR TEACHING STUDENTS CREATIVE THINKING THROUGH MEDIA EDUCATION METHODS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the study of mechanisms for teaching students to think creatively through media education methods, the theoretical aspects of the problem of developing media competence and creativity in students, the pedagogical features of the manifestation of students' intellectual and creative abilities based on modern media education technologies, and the development of students' creative thinking abilities.*

Keywords: *creative thinking, media education, method, media competence, technology, pedagogical characteristic.*

Today, in order to develop students' logical thinking, creative thinking, and creative thinking abilities in the formation of pedagogical features specific to the manifestation of their intellectual abilities, as well as to educate a well-rounded person in all respects, it is necessary to design, plan, organize, control, and manage a modern project based on modern approaches to media educational technologies, and ensuring the effectiveness of this process is a very urgent issue, namely the issue of radically changing the quality of education and training conducted with schoolchildren. This issue is addressed through the introduction of advanced methods of teaching and learning using modern media and educational technologies, the improvement of the mechanisms of intellectual and creative abilities of students, the widespread use of the achievements of world civilization and information resources, the pedagogical features and conditions of the development of interactive exercises, the role of teachers in this process. It will be necessary to give greater importance to issues such as determining the place and content of activities.

In this era of globalization and the ever-expanding scope of information, the need for media educational products that protect secondary school students from this information, support their critical and creative thinking, and help them develop their curiosity and logical thinking, rather than simply accepting it, is growing day by day. The reason is that the priority of the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of expressive-figurative thinking in children of this age also requires that the organization of classes based on media education acquire a more effective character. Today, when students demonstrate their intellectual and creative abilities, they are not reflected in aspects such as "rational thinking", "emotional thinking", "creative thinking", "content thinking", "logical thinking", and the logical type of thinking in students is relatively weak and difficult. Therefore, we should show children the manifestations of logical thinking based on media educational technologies. Another characteristic psychological sign of the manifestation of intellectual and creative abilities of students is the creativity of these children in their thinking. Creativity is the ability to create a product that is relatively new and appropriate to the context in which it is placed. Such a product can be, for example, an idea, a piece of music, a story or an

advertisement. By definition, a new idea is considered original and unexpected, this approach or idea differs from the theory or idea that has been created by itself or by other people before. In addition, its degree of novelty can vary from a minimal difference to a significant novelty from the one that was created earlier. On the other hand, a creative product cannot be new just like that. In addition, it must be adaptable, that is, it must be able to adapt to different forms depending on the person's situation. When studying ideas about creativity in the scientific literature, one usually thinks about novelty and adaptability. It should be emphasized that there are no absolute criteria for assessing the level of creativity of a thought, idea, or product. In practice, assessing creativity involves a social context. When an expert, a group of people, or society as a whole compares their work with other creative products, their level of creativity is assessed. Similarly, the global level of creativity of an individual or group is assessed relative to other people or groups.

As a result of educational reforms, it is important to radically improve the quality of education in schools, vocational colleges and lyceums, and higher educational institutions of the country through the widespread introduction of new information and communication and pedagogical technologies, electronic textbooks, and multimedia tools into the educational process, to strengthen the educational and laboratory base of educational institutions with the most modern educational and laboratory equipment, computer technology, as well as to accelerate the growth of science, technology, and information technology in it, to introduce frequent updates to the development of scientific and technical information. It is known that information and the methods of information transmission require updating and improvement. In the process of primary education, it is advisable to apply such teaching methods that will help students learn to read independently, think, and work creatively with information, ensure that students are oriented towards their own thinking, develop their work skills, increase their interest in reading and independent learning, and the figurative representation of a particular phenomenon or process in the memory of students will enrich the educational material and help it be scientifically mastered. As a result of the inability to correctly analyze the information disseminated through the media and the lack of independent, critical thinking, young people, who are the future of society, are developing difficult character traits. However, the basis of the requirements for a modern mature person is "the ability to have one's own independent opinion, to resist external influences". Regarding media culture, Marshall McLuhan said that "in order for a person to be fully literate, he must first be literate in the world of media" [4;21-23]. Currently, as world psychologists emphasize, "indigo" children are more sensitive to events happening in the world than adults. Therefore, today's educators face a number of urgent tasks. One of them is the use of media education methods in the educational process. Teaching teachers to use media teaching methods rationally, in accordance with the goals and conditions, based on didactic principles, is considered one of the important issues of modern pedagogy today.

Interactive methods of education based on modern pedagogical technologies can provide simplification, clarification of the educational process, freedom and non-obligation of the teacher, and most importantly, high interest and effectiveness for the student. This process is accompanied by significant changes in pedagogical theory and the educational process, which are associated with the introduction of adjustments to the structure of educational technologies, which should correspond to modern technical capabilities and contribute to the child's harmonious entry into the information society. Computer technologies should not be an additional "add-on" to education, but an integral part of the integrated educational process, significantly increasing its effectiveness. The

development of society is characterized by the strong influence of computer technologies on it, penetrating into all spheres of human activity, ensuring the distribution of information flows in society. An integral and important part of these processes is the computerization of education. It is known that in our country, in order to further improve the system of continuous education, improve the services and capabilities of the quality education system, it was announced that it is necessary to establish free use of media products in the teaching process. Determining the availability of opportunities for using computer technologies in primary education is one of the most important indicators of the use of such technologies in the educational process. Taking into account the achievements made in this area, it should be noted that the use of computer technology in the general activities of an educational institution in the following aspects will be effective. Promising directions for the informatization of primary education include the use of modern telecommunications and networked information technologies. The use of such tools opens up new opportunities for secondary schools and higher educational institutions to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. Computers expand educational resources, that is, the possibility of using various multimedia textbooks, electronic books, etc. is becoming widespread. Taking into account these factors, today the implementation of information technologies in practice imposes new requirements on the education system, including the informatization of the educational sphere in primary education, requiring each educational institution to informatize the educational environment. Educational materials on the Internet are widely used. Most of the materials obtained from the Internet are created in multimedia form. For example, for primary grades, these include presentations such as “Whose house is where?”, “Building a house” and various computer games. The introduction of information technologies into the education system opens up wide opportunities for the use of modern teaching methods in the educational process.

For primary school students, it is possible to prepare mixed computer programs that include demonstration-exercise, control-exercise and test modules using a variety of didactic materials. The section “Electronic Information” in the 3rd grade textbook contains instructive stories and colorful pictures, interesting information, and questions for primary school students. Students, having heard the story of an ancient computer, conclude that they should not get into a bad mood by playing games without doing their homework like Salimjon, and that they should be an exemplary student by using the computer correctly and receiving praise from their English teacher like Olimjon.

Determining the availability of opportunities to use computer technologies in primary education is one of the most important indicators of the use of such technologies in the educational process. Taking into account the achievements got in this area, it should be noted that the use of computer technology in the general activities of an educational institution in the following aspects is effective. Promising directions of informatization of primary education imply the use of modern telecommunications and networked information technologies. When using such tools, secondary schools and higher educational institutions open up new opportunities to increase the efficiency of the educational process.[3;11-12] Computers expand educational resources, that is, the possibility of using various multimedia textbooks, e-books, etc. is becoming widespread. Taking this into account, today the implementation of information technologies in practice imposes new requirements on the education system, including the informatization of the educational sphere in primary education, requiring each educational institution to informatize the educational environment.

On December 29, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: “Improving the quality of education is the only correct way for the development of a new Uzbekistan!” got acquainted with the exhibition of modern textbooks on the topic. Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that the cornerstone of progress, the power that makes a country powerful and a nation great, is science, education and upbringing. Therefore, all stages of this sphere are being radically reformed and comprehensively developed. The fourth priority area in the Development Strategy of our country is aimed at the development of the education sector, human capital. In line with this, 2023 was named the “Year of Attention to the Person and Quality Education”. Interactive methods of education based on modern pedagogical technologies can facilitate the educational process, clarify it, and ensure the effectiveness of organizing lesson processes based on the needs of the student.

In conclusion, we can say that the scientific methodological foundations of the use of multimedia tools in the educational process and its effective methods have been proven to date through numerous pedagogical scientific research, practical experimental and test works. Multimedia tools, which have been applied to the teaching process of all subjects in the schools of our republic, have become one of the important tools used by students to master the subject in a short time. Multimedia tools are an effective and promising tool for teaching, which allows the teacher to present a wider range of information than traditional sources of information. I believe that the use of not only text, graphics, diagrams, but also sound, animations, multimedia, video, etc. in a visual and harmonious way creates the opportunity to sequentially select types of information in accordance with the level of perception and logical learning of students.

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